

Improved Neural Ordinary Differential Equation-based Reduced Model for Impinging Jet using Wall Shear Stress

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Modeling the complex flow behavior of impingement jets is a problem of great importance in many industrial applications. Traditional modeling methods often fail to accurately predict these flows due to their nonlinear nature. This paper presents a neural network-based reduced-order model for experimental data of a circular impinging jet and compares several data assimilation frameworks for incorporating wall shear stress measurements obtained from different radial positions. The high-dimensional velocity field and the corresponding wall shear stress measurements are obtained using time-resolved particle image velocimetry (TR-PIV) and polarographic measurements, respectively. The developed reduced-order model results from a proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) step for dimensionality reduction with a neural ordinary differential equation (NODE) for temporal modeling. The performance of the POD-NODE framework is compared with dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) and nonlinear temporal modeling using long short-term memory (LSTM). Assessments are based on root mean squared error and spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD) of the reconstructed predicted solution. It is found that the POD-NODE framework provides the most accurate dynamical model. Furthermore, it is evident that incorporating wall shear stress measurements in the NODE model as additional states significantly improves the prediction accuracy, outperforming traditional filtering techniques such as extended Kalman filters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Impinging jets have been extensively studied over the past five decades due to their significant importance in many industrial applications. Both experimental¹⁻³, and numerical⁴⁻⁶ research efforts have focused on understanding the physics of impinging jet flows. A particular emphasis has been placed on the heat transfer characteristics of these flows, given their importance in cooling applications (see e.g., Plant et al.⁷ for a review of the different jet impingement cooling methods). This is especially relevant in solar energy technologies, where solar collectors, prone to overheating, can benefit from impingement cooling techniques. For example, Javidan and Moghadam⁸ demonstrated that employing an impinging jet cooling system enhanced the thermal and electrical performance of photovoltaic modules by nearly 48%. In addition, impinging jets have found application in textile drying⁹, glass tempering¹⁰, and other engineering applications such as cooling of turbine blades¹¹, and electronic devices¹².

Impinging jet flows can be modeled using the Navier-Stokes equations, which can be solved either for the entire flow domain as a single region (see e.g., Looney and Walsh¹³ for numerical models of laminar free, developing turbulent free, and turbulent impinging jets) or by dividing it into separate regions, namely the free jet, the stagnation zone, and the radial wall-jet region, as suggested by Bradshaw and Love¹⁴, with different approximations applied to each region¹⁵. Both approaches are computationally expensive due to the detailed spatial discretization required to accurately resolve the boundary layer and the near-wall vortex dynamics. This complexity renders optimization, real-time estimation, and control of

impinging flows impractical and highly challenging. Consequently, building reduced-order models (ROMs) for these systems is a viable alternative to address these challenges.

The main objective of reduced-order modeling is to reduce the number of degrees of freedom in a system. This can be accomplished due to the fact that many high-dimensional practical systems can be effectively approximated in low-dimensional reduced spaces spanned by tailored bases. These bases can be identified from data using techniques such as proper orthogonal decomposition (POD)¹⁶ or autoencoders¹⁷. Reduced-order modeling techniques are classified into two main categories, namely intrusive and non-intrusive methods, where the former requires access to the governing equations of the underlying system, while the latter is data-driven. Galerkin projection is a widely used technique within the intrusive category (see, e.g., Sommer et al.¹⁸ for a practical engineering application). However, when the governing equations are not accessible due to proprietary software or when the system dynamics is studied experimentally, as in our case, constructing projection-based ROMs is not feasible. In such scenarios, the focus shifts to building non-intrusive ROMs purely from data, using methods such as dynamic mode decomposition (DMD)¹⁹ or radial basis function interpolation²⁰.

Recent advances in machine learning enabled modeling the dynamics within the reduced space using deep neural networks, rather than using ordinary differential equations derived from the Galerkin-projection onto the governing equations. In this context, various architectures have been proposed. For instance, Pawar et al.²¹ employed a fully connected neural network to model the dynamics within the POD space. The outputs of the network are residuals that update the

states according to the defined integration scheme. Wu et al.²² utilized temporal convolutional layers with residual blocks to predict the subsequent state vector within the POD space. In addition, long short-term memory (LSTM) layers have been used for the same purpose in conjunction with POD^{23,24} and autoencoder-based reduction techniques^{25,26}. More recently, transformer neural networks have been applied to model the discrete dynamics within the reduced space²⁷.

Most previous studies utilize neural networks to model the discrete dynamics of the system, either in high-dimensional or reduced spaces. Some have employed neural networks to predict the residual updates for various integration schemes, such as the explicit Euler method in San et al.²⁸, the two-step Adams-Bashforth method in Pawar et al.²¹, and the 4-th order Runge-Kutta method in Zhang et al.²⁹. However, these models typically train the neural network to predict the residuals corresponding to a specific integration scheme. This limitation has been addressed by Lui et al.³⁰ by training a neural network to predict the temporal derivatives, which can then be integrated using any integration method. However, this approach requires performing an expensive and accurate numerical differentiation step to prepare the training data. Alternatively, other methods model the dynamics in continuous time using, e.g., neural ordinary differential equations (NODE)³¹, where the outputs of the neural network are treated as implicit intermediate outputs, and the training is based on actual subsequent states. These continuous models have a more general representation of the dynamics of the system because they allow non-uniform temporal predictions. It should be noted that other methods have also been proposed for learning continuous dynamics such as the PDE-based network³², and the sparse identification of nonlinear dynamical systems³³, to name just a few.

Few previous studies have utilized NODE within the reduced-order modeling framework. Maulik et al.³⁴ employed NODE to model latent dynamics within the POD space for a one-dimensional Burger's problem. Rojas et al.³⁵ developed a generative NODE architecture to forecast the latent dynamics of the Von Karman vortex street. Furthermore, Kanaa et al.³⁶ used NODE for simple video generation with the moving MNIST dataset featuring 1 and 2 digits. Dutta et al.³⁷ compared the behavior of NODE-based ROMs with methods based on radial basis function interpolation and DMD for a shallow water hydrodynamics example. In the present work, we further explore the potential of modeling the latent dynamics in the reduced space using NODE, specifically applied to complex, real-world experimental data of a circular impinging jet. Additionally, we aim to assist the predictions by incorporating wall shear stress within a data assimilation framework.

The correlation between the wall shear stress and the vortex dynamics in a circular impinging jet has been studied by El Hassan et al.^{38,39}. It has been shown that the primary and secondary vortical structures significantly influence the variation of the wall shear stress. Specifically, the vortex ring, along with the secondary and tertiary vortices near the wall, are the main mechanisms affecting the wall shear stress signals. This correlation is also expected to manifest in the reduced space. Consequently, the wall shear stress measure-

FIG. 1: Experimental setup of the impinging jet. It consists of (1) circular disc, (2) cylindrical tube, (3) pump, (4) reservoir, (5) laser head, (6) camera, (7) support, and (8) cooling coil.

ments can be used to assist model predictions of the complex underlying flow. Specifically, the wall shear stress measurements can be used to estimate the latent vector in the POD space^{40,41}. Various methods have been employed for this estimation, including the extended POD method^{42,43}, which provides a linear relationship between the measurements and the POD latent vector, the extended Kalman filter⁴⁴, and deep learning approaches⁴⁵. In parallel, recent efforts have focused on developing neural network-based methods for reconstructing high dimensional flow fields directly from sparse measurements, without an intermediate reduction step. For example, Erichson et al.⁴⁶ developed an end-to-end shallow neural network with no prior knowledge of the system. Fukami et al.⁴⁷ used Voronoi tessellation-assisted deep learning to handle an arbitrary number of moving sensors. Wu et al.⁴⁸ introduced a deep-learning method based on the compressed sensing DMD to overcome the random sensor distribution limitation.

In a similar application involving an impinging jet, a data assimilation framework based on the shear stress transport model has been developed for predicting flow characteristics at various Reynolds numbers and nozzle-to-plate distances⁴⁹. Additionally, coarse wall measurements of a turbulent open channel flow have been used to generate high-resolution flow fields using a super-resolution generative model⁵⁰. Surface measurements for free surface flows have also been employed to predict the corresponding three-dimensional flow beneath the surface using a convolutional neural network⁵¹. However, to the best of our knowledge, the present work represents the first practical use of experimental wall shear stress measurements to build ROM of a turbulent impinging jet, for both LSTM and NODE. Specifically, we introduce an end-to-end filtering framework based on NODE for the polarographic wall shear stress measurements and evaluate its performance in comparison to traditional methods, such as the extended Kalman filter.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the techniques used in this work for data-driven modeling of high-dimensional flow fields, along with

FIG. 2: Spatial representation of the temporal means for both velocity components.

their mathematical formulations. The experimental setup is detailed in Sec. III. Section IV outlines the proposed framework for incorporating wall shear stress measurements into flow field predictions. The results are presented in Sec. V. Finally, the paper concludes in Sec. VI.

II. DATA-DRIVEN MODELING OF FLOW FIELDS

Data-driven modeling of flow fields is challenged by the curse of dimensionality. This issue arises due to the high-dimensional spatial discretization required for numerical simulations and the high-resolution cameras used in experimental setups. Fortunately, flow field data are typically embedded in low-dimensional manifolds, where dominant patterns emerge. Consequently, data-driven modeling of flow fields generally involves two main steps:

1. dimensionality reduction to identify these dominant patterns,
2. dynamical modeling within the reduced space.

A. Dimensionality reduction using proper orthogonal decomposition (POD)

POD is a technique used to extract dominant features within a dataset. In POD, the low-dimensional manifold \mathcal{M} is a linear vector space and is spanned by a set of vectors known as the POD modes $\{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_d\} \subset \mathbb{R}^N$. Here, d denotes the dimension of \mathcal{M} , representing the number of dominant modes

(dominant based on their kinetic energy content), and $N \gg d$ denotes the spatial dimension of the original dataset.

FIG. 3: POD energy curve of the velocity fluctuation component. The rank of truncation is 50.

Consider the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ constructed by concatenating a set of uniformly distributed snapshots $\mathbf{q}(t_m)$, where $m = 1, \dots, M$:

$$\mathbf{D} = [\mathbf{q}(t_1) \quad \mathbf{q}(t_2) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{q}(t_M)]. \quad (1)$$

The POD modes are defined as the eigenvectors of the correlation matrix $\mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$:

$$\mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T \Phi = \Phi \Lambda. \quad (2)$$

This eigenvalue problem is related to the singular value decomposition of the snapshot matrix \mathbf{D} , given by

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{V}^T, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$ are orthonormal matrices. Here, $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ is rectangular diagonal matrix with singular values $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r$, where $r = \text{rank}(\mathbf{D})$. It can be demonstrated that the left singular vectors of \mathbf{D} are the POD modes, i.e., $\Phi = \mathbf{U}$, and the corresponding eigenvalues of the POD modes are the squares of the singular values of \mathbf{D} , i.e., $\Lambda = \Sigma^2$.

Within the linear reduced space \mathcal{M} , each flow snapshot is approximated as a linear combination of the d most dominant POD modes (first d columns of \mathbf{U}):

$$\mathbf{q}(t_m) \approx \tilde{\mathbf{q}}(t_m) = \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_i a_i(t_m), \quad (4)$$

where $a_i(t_m)$ is the temporal coefficient associated to the i -th POD mode. The accuracy of the low-rank approximation presented in (4) is controlled by the number of POD modes, which can be quantified by their retained energy content η , defined as

$$\eta = \frac{\sum_{j=0}^d \sigma_j^2}{\sum_{j=0}^r \sigma_j^2} \times 100. \quad (5)$$

B. Latent dynamics modeling

Once the low-dimensional manifold \mathcal{M} is identified, the goal becomes predicting the dynamics within \mathcal{M} , represented by the vector of temporal coefficients $\mathbf{a}(t_m) = [a_i(t_m) \cdots a_d(t_m)]^T$ in (4).

1. Dynamic mode decomposition (DMD)

In DMD, the linear space \mathcal{M} is slightly different from the space identified using the POD method. Specifically, DMD modes are computed such that each mode corresponds to a distinct oscillatory frequency. In contrast, POD modes are obtained by maximizing the variance (energy) in the dataset, without directly considering the temporal dynamics. As a result, the evolution of the temporal coefficients $a_i(t)$ corresponding to each POD mode may involve contributions from more than a single frequency, as evident in Fig. 7.

Mathematically, the DMD method seeks to model the dynamics of the flow with a linear operator, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{D}' \approx \mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{A} models a time shift and $\mathbf{D}' = [\mathbf{q}(t_2) \ \mathbf{q}(t_3) \ \cdots \ \mathbf{q}(t_{M+1})]$ is the lagged matrix. The high-dimensional linear operator \mathbf{A} can be represented as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{D}'\mathbf{D}^\dagger$, where \mathbf{D}^\dagger is the Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse of \mathbf{D} , obtained using the singular value decomposition shown in (3), i.e., $\mathbf{D}^\dagger = \mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}^*$, which implies

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{D}'\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}^*. \quad (7)$$

The DMD modes Ψ and the eigenvalues Ξ are defined as the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , respectively. However, direct computation of \mathbf{A} using (7) and solving its eigenvalue problem is computationally expensive, especially for large dimensions ($N \gg 1$). To address this, we project \mathbf{A} onto a reduced space of dimension d spanned by the first d columns of \mathbf{U} :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{D}'\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

The eigendecomposition of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{W} = \Xi\mathbf{W}, \quad (9)$$

provides the DMD eigenvalues Ξ , which are at the same time the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} . The DMD modes Ψ , i.e., eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} are then obtained by

$$\Psi = \mathbf{S}'\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{W}. \quad (10)$$

The reader is referred to Schmid⁵² for a comprehensive review of the DMD method and its variants.

2. Long short-term memory layer (LSTM)

LSTM layers are a special type of recurrent neural network introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber⁵³ to address the

vanishing or exploding gradients problem often encountered in training conventional recurrent layers. LSTMs can model the dynamics within the reduced space \mathcal{M} , which can be identified using techniques such as POD. Unlike conventional recurrent neural networks which utilize only the current state x_t and the previous state h_{t-1} , which reflects the short-term memory, LSTM layers introduce a cell state c_t . This cell state is introduced to store and manage long-term memory. The flow of information within an LSTM layer is regulated using a gating mechanism consisting of candidate, forget, input, and output gates. Mathematically, these gates are defined by the following series of equations, respectively:

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_{g,x}x_t + W_{g,h}h_{t-1} + b_g), \quad (11)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{f,x}x_t + W_{f,h}h_{t-1} + b_f), \quad (12)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{e,x}x_t + W_{e,h}h_{t-1} + b_e), \quad (13)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_{o,x}x_t + W_{o,h}h_{t-1} + b_o), \quad (14)$$

where, W_{\cdot} represents weight matrices associated with each gate, while b_{\cdot} signifies bias vectors, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ denotes the sigmoid function. The candidate gate evaluates the current state x_t and the previous short-term state h_{t-1} to propose a potential update \tilde{c}_t to the cell state. The forget gate then determines the extent to which the previous cell state c_{t-1} should be retained or forgotten by assigning a value f_t between 0 and 1 through the sigmoid function (0 means completely forgetting). Similarly, the input gate regulates how much of the candidate state \tilde{c}_t should be incorporated into the cell state, using a value i_t between 0 and 1. Finally, the output gate decides how much of the updated cell state c_t should be passed to the output h_t , through a value o_t between 0 and 1. According to the forget and input rates obtained from (12) and (13), respectively, the current cell state c_t is updated through

$$c_t = f_t c_{t-1} + i_t \tilde{c}_t, \quad (15)$$

where multiplication is element-wise. Finally, the output h_t of the LSTM layer, which is the new short-term memory at the subsequent timestep, is obtained based on the candidate value obtained from (11) and the output rate obtained from (14), i.e.,

$$h_t = o_t \tanh(c_t). \quad (16)$$

To ensure accurate LSTM predictions, it is common practice to feed the network a long input sequence to initialize the memory and update the cell states effectively. In addition, LSTMs are well-suited for modeling discrete dynamics, leading to predicted values that are uniformly distributed²⁴.

3. Neural ordinary differential equation (NODE)

In contrast to discrete model structures such as fully connected, recurrent, and residual neural networks, which provide discrete model structures, NODEs provide a basis for modeling the dynamics of the system in continuous time. This is enabled by considering the output layer of a neural network as

FIG. 4: Spatial representation of the six most dominant POD modes $\phi_i(\mathbf{x})$, $i = 1, \dots, 6$, ordered from top to bottom for (left) radial and (right) axial velocity components.

the implicit solution, representing the black-box ordinary differential equation. Such a model structure can be represented in the POD space by the following equation:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{a}(t)}{dt} = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{a}(t), t, \theta), \quad (17)$$

where f_{θ} is a fully connected neural network, parameterized by θ . The given equation represents a velocity field of the state vector. This function can then be used to simulate the

system's state vector forward in time using an arbitrary numerical integration scheme. Throughout this work, we considered the Euler-Trapezoidal integration scheme for simulating the NODE models, which can be mathematically represented as

FIG. 5: Evaluation of the linear measurement model between the temporal coefficients and the wall shear stress signals.

follows:

$$\mathbf{a}(t_0 + \Delta t) = \mathbf{a}(t_0) + \underbrace{\int_{t_0}^{t_0 + \Delta t} f_{\theta}(\mathbf{a}(t), t) dt}_{\Phi}, \quad (18a)$$

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{2} \Delta t f_{\theta}(\mathbf{a}(t_0), t_0) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t f_{\theta}(\mathbf{a}(t_0 + \Delta t), t_0 + \Delta t), \quad (18b)$$

where Δt denotes the integration step size.

In the original paper³¹, the authors state and provide evidence for numerous advantages of NODE over explicit model structures, such as adaptive computation provided by modern ODE solvers, parameter efficiency, smooth prediction trajectories, the ability to work with irregularly sampled data, etc. The authors also tackle the challenge of memory efficiency within the training process and propose the use of the adjoint sensitivity method⁵⁴ to perform backpropagation through the ODE solver. Typically, when training such models, we backpropagate through every operation in the ODE solver to calculate gradients, which can be memory-intensive. However, the adjoint sensitivity method allows for calculating the gradients without the need to store all intermediate states of the ODE solver in memory. Yet, in the meantime, the use of the adjoint sensitivity method has been criticized by the community^{55–57}, because it involves more numerical errors in reverse mode computation compared to the classical backpropagation through time method⁵⁸. This is caused by forgetting the forward-time computational trajectories. In other words, when training the NODE model, one is left

to choose between the memory-efficient adjoint sensitivity method or the backpropagation through time method, which comes with higher numerical accuracy. In this study, we opt to use the backpropagation through time method for training NODE models, as the size of our models does not demand the memory savings provided by the adjoint method. More importantly, using backpropagation through time allows us to maintain consistency in the training methods between NODE and LSTM networks, ensuring a fair comparison.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of several key components arranged to facilitate precise measurements of the fluid flow and wall shear stress. Central to the setup is a circular disc, which serves as the target surface for the impinging jet. The fluid is delivered to this disc through a cylindrical tube connected to a pump that draws the fluid from a reservoir. Above the setup, a laser head and a high-speed camera are positioned to capture the flow dynamics, aided by a support structure that provides stability and alignment. The temperature of the fluid is regulated by a cooling coil to ensure consistent experimental conditions. This arrangement allows for a detailed analysis of the flow and shear characteristics as the fluid impacts the disc.

The experiment is designed to measure both the 2D velocity field and the wall shear stress in an impinging jet using particle image velocimetry (PIV) and the polarographic method,

respectively. The setup includes a gear pump that circulates an electrolyte solution from a reservoir through a nozzle. This fluid then impinges on a circular target disk that has electrodes embedded in it. The temperature of the fluid is precisely controlled within $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ using a cooling coil.

The nozzle is attached to a stainless steel tube and is fitted with a honeycomb structure to stabilize the flow. The nozzle can be moved vertically for precise alignment with the target disk. The reservoir is positioned on a sliding table, allowing movement in multiple directions with high precision. To minimize disturbances in the measurements, a transparent plate is used to reduce surface waves in the area where a laser penetrates the electrochemical solution.

The target disk, made of Plexiglas, has a diameter of 50 mm and features platinum electrodes for measuring the wall shear stress. The four electrodes, indicated by horizontal lines on the circular disk in Fig. 1, are positioned at radii of 3.4 mm, 7.3 mm, 12.3 mm, and 17.3 mm. These electrodes are carefully prepared and aligned to ensure accurate measurements. The platinum foil on the disk acts as the anode in the electrochemical setup. The fluid used is a specific solution of potassium ferrocyanide with potassium sulfate, which provides known physical properties such as density and viscosity. The nozzle design, including its diameter and length, and the distance from the nozzle exit to the target disk, are carefully controlled to achieve the desired flow characteristics.

Measurements were conducted at a Reynolds number $Re = 1260$ based on the jet exit diameter and the centerline exit velocity using a PIV system. This system consists of an Nd:YLF NewWave Pegasus laser, emitting a wavelength of 527 nm and 10 mJ energy, and a Phantom V9 camera with a resolution of 1200×1632 pixels. The setup captures detailed flow patterns by tracking the movement of small glass spheres suspended in the fluid. The data is then processed to calculate the velocity components, ensuring high spatial resolution and accuracy. During a 1 second interval, 500 PIV images were captured. For wall shear stress measurements, the polarographic method was used, which involves calculating the limiting diffusion current on the electrodes. Corrections are applied to account for any measurement errors, ensuring precise determination of wall shear stress using the measured wall shear rate and the fluid's viscosity. The reader is referred to El Hassan et al.³⁹ for more details about the experimental setup.

IV. REDUCED-ORDER MODEL USING WALL SHEAR STRESS MEASUREMENTS

Given a PIV snapshot $\mathbf{s}(t_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_y \times N_c}$ at timestep t_m , we define $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c}$ as the velocity vector field, comprising the N_c velocity components (see Fig. 2 for the temporal means of the radial and axial components considered in the present work), at location \mathbf{x} in the Cartesian grid of dimensions $N_x \times N_y$. The first step in constructing a ROM is to reduce the high-dimensional space resulting from the high resolution of the camera. This is achieved using a dimensionality reduction technique, such as the POD method employed in our work. This process involves decomposing the velocity vec-

tors into their temporal mean $\bar{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x})$ and fluctuation component $\mathbf{u}'(\mathbf{x}, t_m)$. The goal of the ROM is to predict the fluctuation component, which can be expressed as a linear combination of the dominant flow structure obtained using POD, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t_m) = \bar{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{u}'(\mathbf{x}, t_m) = \bar{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_i(\mathbf{x}) a_i(t_m), \quad (19)$$

where d denotes the dimension of the POD basis. The spatial representation of the temporal means for both velocity components is shown in Fig. 2. The rank d of the POD truncation, set to 50 modes in our case, is chosen to ensure that 92.5% of the flow energy content is retained using the low-rank POD approximation. This rank corresponds to the elbow point of the energy curve shown in Fig. 3, where adding more modes does not substantially increase the captured energy, and the curve starts to flatten. The six most dominant POD modes are visualized in Fig. 4. The two most dominant modes exhibit only large-scale vortices around the stagnation point for both velocity components. In contrast, the third and fourth modes display vortices farther from the stagnation point in the radial direction. Modes 5 and 6 consist mainly of small-scale vortices distributed near the wall. A comparison between the low-rank POD approximation using 50 modes with the original PIV snapshot at timesteps 370 and 420 for radial and axial velocity components is presented in the first 2 rows of Figs. 8 and 9, respectively. We note that the POD modes are obtained from the first 400 PIV snapshots. The POD-truncated approximation is in very good agreement with the original solution, especially near the stagnation point. However, slight deviations are observed farther in the radial direction. Consequently, our model will not accurately predict the flow in this region since it will be trained on the low-rank approximation, which will be treated as the ground truth in our evaluation later.

Once the reduced space \mathcal{M} is identified, the objective of the ROM is to predict the dynamics of the system within \mathcal{M} . This involves predicting the evolution of the temporal coefficients vector $\mathbf{a}(t_m)$. Most data-driven ROMs achieve this by fitting a neural network \mathcal{F} to predict the temporal coefficients vector at the next discrete time step, given a sequence of prior states, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{a}(t_{m+1}) = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}(t_m), \mathbf{a}(t_{m-1}), \dots, \mathbf{a}(t_{m-H+1})), \quad (20)$$

where H denotes the length of the input sequence considered. However, this approach only allows the predictions at uniformly sampled time intervals. Additionally, recurrent neural networks, which are commonly used for this type of modeling, require long input sequences for reliable predictions and are prone to overfitting. Therefore, we use NODE to model the vector field of our state vector, specifically the temporal coefficients vector of our flow field, i.e., $\dot{\mathbf{a}}(t_m) = f_\theta(\mathbf{a}(t_m))$, as shown in (17). By doing so, we can employ an accurate numerical integrator to advance the state vector forward in time, providing more flexibility. Algorithm 1 summarizes the POD-NODE ROM framework, where we use the Euler-Trapezoidal integration scheme as defined in (18).

FIG. 6: Schematic of the end-to-end filtering approach for the wall shear stress measurements within the POD-NODE framework.

Algorithm 1 POD-NODE ROM framework

Require: Φ , \mathcal{N} , initial snapshot $\mathbf{s}(t_0)$, number of predictions P ;

- 1: Reshape $\mathbf{s}(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_y \times N_c}$ to a vector $\mathbf{v}(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_x \cdot N_y \cdot N_c)}$;
- 2: Project $\mathbf{v}(t_0)$ onto \mathcal{M} : $\mathbf{a}(t_0) = \Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{v}(t_0)$;
- 3: **for** $m = 1, \dots, P$ **do**
- 4: Predict velocity vector $\hat{\mathbf{a}}(t_m) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{a}(t_m))$;
- 5: Integrate $\mathbf{a}(t_{m+1}) = \text{Solve}(\hat{\mathbf{a}}(t_m))$;
- 6: Add to the prediction array $\mathbf{A} \leftarrow \mathbf{a}(t_{m+1})$;
- 7: **end for**
- 8: Reconstruct corresponding flow fields $\mathbf{V} = \Phi \cdot \mathbf{A}$;
- 9: Reshape $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_x \cdot N_y \cdot N_c) \times P}$ to $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_y \times N_c \times P}$;
- 10: **return** \mathbf{S}

The neural network in the NODE framework is trained implicitly by updating the network parameters to minimize the following cost function

$$J = \frac{1}{d \times N_h} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^{N_h} (a_i(t_j) - \hat{a}_i(t_j))^2, \quad (21)$$

where N_h denotes the length of the prediction horizon, i.e., the length of simulated rollouts using a single initial condition, and $a_i(t_j)$ and $\hat{a}_i(t_j)$ denote the ground truth and the predicted temporal coefficient values, respectively. The network parameters are optimized using the gradient descent algorithm or one of its variants. The backpropagation through time method⁵⁸ is employed to compute the gradients of the ODE solver and the network.

Algorithm 2 NODE-EKF

Require: \mathcal{G} , $\mathbf{P}(0)$, \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R}

- 1: **Initialize:** $m = 1$, $\mathbf{a}^{\text{EKF}}(0) = \mathbf{0}$
- 2: **while** true **do**
- 3: **Predictor:**
- 4: measure $\mathbf{w}(t_m)$;
- 5: predict using the NODE model $\mathbf{a}(t_m^-) = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{a}(t_{m-1}))$;
- 6: Compute Jacobian $\mathbf{J}(t_m^-) = \nabla \mathcal{G} \Big|_{\mathbf{a}(t_{m-1})}$
- 7: estimate prediction covariance $\mathbf{P}(t_m^-) = \mathbf{J}(t_m^-) \cdot \mathbf{P}(t_{m-1}) \cdot \mathbf{J}(t_m^-)^T + \mathbf{Q}$
- 8: **Corrector:**
- 9: find Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}(t_m) = \mathbf{P}(t_m^-) \cdot \mathbf{C}^T [\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{P}(t_m^-) \cdot \mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{R}]^{-1}$
- 10: correct predictions $\mathbf{a}^{\text{EKF}}(t_m) = \mathbf{a}(t_m^-) + \mathbf{K}(t_m) [\mathbf{w}(t_m) - \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}(t_m^-)]$
- 11: correct prediction covariance $\mathbf{P}(t_m) = [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}(t_m) \cdot \mathbf{C}] \cdot \mathbf{P}(t_m^-)$
- 12: $m \leftarrow m + 1$
- 13: **end while**

The NODE model enables us to identify a data-driven ROM for our flow, which will be evaluated in Sect. V and compared with DMD and LSTM models. However, our primary objective is to incorporate the available wall shear stress measurements into the predictions. To achieve this, we consider standard filtering methods, such as the extended Kalman filter, as well as an end-to-end approach that integrates the filtering problem directly within the neural network.

A. Extended Kalman filter

We denote \mathcal{G} as the NODE model comprising both, the neural network and the ODE solver. We utilize the extended Kalman filter (EKF) to estimate the temporal coefficients vector $\mathbf{a}(t_m)$ from the wall shear stress measurements $\mathbf{w}(t_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$, where N_s denotes the number of polarographic sensors. The sensor signals are shown in Fig. 5, with w_i representing the wall shear stress signal for the i -th sensor, for $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. The extended Kalman filter requires a measurement model that maps the predicted states, i.e., the vector of temporal coefficients, to the corresponding measurements. Using the first 400 timesteps, we fit a linear measurement model of the form $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}(t_m) = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}(t_m)$, where $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s \times d}$ is the output matrix, and $\tilde{\mathbf{w}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$ is the predicted vector of wall shear stress measurements. \mathbf{C} is obtained by solving the least-squares problem

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{C}} \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{400} \mathbf{w}(t_m) - \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}(t_m) \right\|_2^2. \quad (22)$$

The evaluation of the measurement model, presented in Fig. 5, shows that the first 3 wall shear stress signals are linearly correlated with the temporal coefficients. However, this is not the case for the last signal, where the model deviates in the validation region. Despite this deviation, we will use the linear model in the EKF algorithm due to its simplicity and high accuracy in predicting the first three sensor signals. The NODE-EKF approach is outlined in Algorithm 2. The NODE model predicts $\mathbf{a}(t_m^-)$, where t_m^- is the time immediately before the next measurement becomes available at time t_m . In the EKF algorithm, the NODE model \mathcal{G} is linearized, and the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}(t_m^-)$ is used to estimate the prediction covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}(t_m^-)$. Next, the wall shear stress measurement vector $\mathbf{w}(t_m)$ is used to correct the predicted temporal coefficient values, yielding the corrected vector $\mathbf{a}^{\text{EKF}}(t_m)$. The matrices $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ and $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s \times N_s}$ denote the covariance matrices of the prediction and the measurement, respectively. Typically, these matrices are set as scaled unit matrices, where a higher scaling factor in \mathbf{Q} reflects less confidence in the NODE predictions, and a higher scaling factor in \mathbf{R} indicates less confidence in the measurements. The matrix $\mathbf{K}(t_m)$, known as the Kalman gain, determines the correction value, which is weighted by the deviation between the measurement vector $\mathbf{w}(t_m)$ and the predicted vector $\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}(t_m^-)$. The matrix $\mathbf{P}(t_m)$ represents the corrected prediction covariance matrix.

B. End-to-end filter

In this approach, we propose extending the input vector of the NODE-ROM to include the wall shear stress values at every timestep. This extension functions as an end-to-end filter, enabling the NODE model to learn how to map the extended state vector, comprising the temporal coefficients and the available measurements, to the subsequent state vector. The end-to-end approach is illustrated in Fig. 6. After projecting the high-dimensional snapshot onto the POD space, the

NODE model takes the vector of temporal coefficients $\mathbf{a}(t_m)$ and the measurements vector $\mathbf{w}(t_m)$ as inputs to predict the subsequent vector of temporal coefficients $\mathbf{a}(t_{m+1})$. This approach differs from other end-to-end filtering methods, such as the end-to-end shallow neural network⁴⁶, where the neural network directly maps the measurements to the corresponding state vector. In contrast, we treat here the measurements as additional states, which are updated at every time step. The neural network parameters are optimized as previously described by minimizing the loss function given in (21) in an autoregressive manner. Once the dynamics are predicted in the POD space for P future timesteps, the high-dimensional solution is easily reconstructed using the POD modes.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we evaluate and compare the performance of various ROMs in predicting flow fields for our experimental setup. Moreover, we assess different methods for incorporating wall shear stress measurements into our predictions.

A. Assessment of the NODE reduced-order model

The NODE model consists of a fully connected neural network, with its detailed architecture shown in Tab. I, followed by an Euler-Trapezoidal method. The hyperparameters of the neural network are tuned manually to obtain the best possible performance. The learnable parameters of the network are optimized using Adam⁵⁹ with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 34. The prediction horizon is set to $N_h = 12$ in the corresponding cost function shown in (21). We compare the performance of the NODE model to that of an LSTM neural network, which has been trained with windowed sequences of length 12. The hyperparameters of the LSTM network, shown in Tab. I, are chosen such that both NODE and LSTM models have the same number of trainable parameters, allowing a fair comparison. To avoid overfitting, a dropout rate of 0.2 was applied before the final dense layers of both models. Additionally, we use the same optimizer hyperparameters to train the LSTM model. Both models have been trained using only the first 400 snapshots. The evaluation consists of starting from a random initial condition between timesteps 0 and 400 (150 in our case) and recursively predicting the complete sequence, i.e., we feed the outputs of each timestep as the inputs in the subsequent timestep. This evaluation procedure ensures that the model did not merely learn the training sequence and examines its robustness to various initial conditions. We emphasize that the LSTM model requires an initial window of 12 timesteps to initialize the memory of the network. In contrast, the NODE model requires only one initial value, which is considered an advantage over the LSTM network. The original and the predicted time series for the temporal coefficients corresponding to the six most dominant POD modes (see Fig. 4 for a visual representation of the corresponding POD modes) are depicted in Fig. 7. Results show that both models have very similar prediction performance, especially for the coeffi-

FIG. 7: Time series for the temporal coefficients corresponding to the six most dominant energy modes. The blue solid line corresponds to the ground truth values, the orange dashed line shows the NODE predictions, and the green dotted line shows the LSTM results. The initial condition for the NODE model is the vector of temporal coefficients corresponding to timestep 150, while the LSTM model uses the preceding 11 timesteps in addition to timestep 150.

TABLE I: Detailed architectures of the neural networks.

NODE		LSTM	
Layer	Output	Layer	Output
Input	50	Input	(12,50)
Dense, mish	400	LSTM, tanh	(12,184)
Dense, mish	400	LSTM, tanh	(12,140)
Dense, mish	400	Dense, sigmoid	50
Dense, mish	50	-	-

coefficients corresponding to the first 2 modes. Moreover, we observe that the predicted values in the validation zone slightly deviate from the ground truth due to error accumulation. Nevertheless, both models remain stable for the considered number of predictions.

We further evaluate the models by reconstructing the high-dimensional solution from the predicted temporal coefficients. Two exemplary snapshots, depicted in Figs. 8 and 9, illustrate radial and axial velocity components, respectively. The reconstructed snapshots are compared with the original and low-rank approximation obtained from the POD truncation of 50 modes, representing the best approximation achievable by our models. Additionally, predictions from the well-established

DMD method, fitted using the first 400 snapshots and evaluated starting from timestep 150, are also presented. It is evident from Figs. 8 and 9 that both LSTM and NODE models outperform DMD in accurately predicting the various vortical scales around the wall. Specifically, the DMD prediction tends to be damped and converges to zero for longer time predictions due to the linear structure of the identified model. This is particularly noticeable when comparing DMD snapshots at timesteps 370 and 420, where the latter one only weakly predicts the formation of vortices around the stagnation points and fails to capture vortex shedding further in the radial direction. On the other hand, LSTM and NODE models remain stable over the considered prediction length. Notably, the vortex shedding structure remains visible and is almost indistinguishable from the ground truth solution at timestep 370, which is near the end of the seen training period. For unseen predictions, e.g., timestep 420, both NODE and LSTM models accurately predict the vortex formation around the stagnation point and the vortex shedding structure, with only slight deviations, particularly in the radial velocity component shown in Fig. 8. For a more quantitative comparison between the developed ROMs, we compute the temporal average root mean squared error (RMSE) for all predicted timesteps between the PIV and predicted flow fields. The results, shown

FIG. 8: Comparison of snapshots obtained from various ROMs for the radial velocity component at two distinct timesteps.

FIG. 9: Comparison of snapshots obtained from various ROMs for the axial velocity component at two distinct timesteps.

in Fig. 10, are compared with the best achievable RMSE corresponding to the low-rank POD approximation. It can be seen that the NODE model, using only one initial condition, performs slightly better than the LSTM model with an input sequence of length 12 (LSTM-12 in Fig. 10). We note that running the LSTM model with only one initial condition (LSTM-1 in Fig. 10) is the least accurate among all others. Furthermore, when considering only the last 100 timesteps, the NODE model achieves a lower RMSE of 0.0089 ms^{-1} compared to the LSTM with 0.00986 ms^{-1} RMSE.

We further evaluate the ROMs by comparing the frequency spectra of the reconstructed solutions using spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD). Unlike POD, which provides a decomposition in the time domain, SPOD determines dominant flow structures at specific frequencies. This makes it particularly suitable for assessing how well each ROM captures the underlying physics across different frequencies. The low-rank approximation of a snapshot $\mathbf{q}(t_m)$ using SPOD can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{q}(t_m) \approx \tilde{\mathbf{q}}(t_m) = \sum_f \sum_{j=1}^d \phi_j(f) \hat{a}_j(f) e^{2\pi i f t_m}, \quad (23)$$

where $\hat{a}_j(f)$ is the Fourier coefficient associated with the j -th mode $\phi_j(f)$ at frequency f . The term $e^{2\pi i f t_m}$ enters for the inverse Fourier transform, encapsulating the temporal evolution at frequency f . The main difference between SPOD and the POD low-rank approximation shown in (4) is that the SPOD involves a summation over multiple frequencies, with each frequency associated with a distinct set of modes. For more details on SPOD, we refer the reader to Schmidt and Colonius⁶⁰. The results of the SPOD analysis are depicted in Fig. 11. The low-rank POD truncation of the original PIV images primarily filters out the measurement noise, as its energy spectrum aligns very well with the original in the low-frequency range (up to 32 Hz, where it starts to deviate). The deviation in the high-frequency region reflects the damping of smaller-scale vortices, particularly those away from the stagnation point, as shown in Figs. 8 and 9. We emphasize that this is the best possible approximation the ROMs are able to achieve since we trained them on the temporal coefficients of the POD space. Furthermore, while the DMD method captures some of the larger-scale structures, it loses track of the flow structure as time progresses, which is evident from Figs. 8 and 9, and the high damping for all frequencies evident from Fig. 11. Specifically, the DMD results exhibit a damping ratio between 2.1 and 2.8 in the low-frequency domain, with this discrepancy increasing significantly at higher frequencies, reaching a damping ratio of approximately 200 at 100 Hz. In contrast, the NODE and LSTM models show relatively good alignment with their corresponding ground truth. The NODE model exhibits slight superiority in the low-frequency range, where the energy spectrum of the LSTM predictions progressively dampens over the frequency range, reaching a ratio of 1.45 at 32 Hz. In comparison, the NODE maintains a ratio close to 1. Beyond this frequency, the NODE model tends to deviate from the ground truth and dampens high-frequency content more than the LSTM model. Despite its accuracy, the

FIG. 10: Comparison of the temporal average RMSE for various ROMs. The presented values are the average of both velocity components. POD truncation yields the best achievable error. The numbers in LSTM-XX refer to the length of the input sequence of the LSTM model.

NODE model exhibits minor discrepancies, which motivates us to enhance its predictions by incorporating wall shear stress measurements.

B. Predictions using wall shear stress measurements

In this section, we compare various methods for incorporating the polarographic wall shear stress (WSS) measurements into our predictions. Specifically, we compare the EKF approach to the end-to-end approach mentioned in Sec. IV. We refer to the latter one as the NODE-WSS model. The original and the predicted coefficients from the NODE-WSS model are depicted in Fig. 12. The evaluation is performed similarly to the ROMs mentioned earlier, starting from timestep 150 and predicting recursively until the end of the time series, with the corresponding wall shear stress measurements fed in at every timestep. Compared to the predicted signals shown in Fig. 7, the predictions have improved, particularly in the validation zone. This improvement is due to the wall shear stress measurements providing information about the near-wall vortex dynamics. This is evident from the strong correlation between wall shear stress signals and the temporal coefficients of the dominant modes. For instance, w_1 and w_2 signals, shown in Fig. 5, correlate well with temporal coefficients of modes 1 and 2, and the w_3 signal correlates with temporal coefficients of modes 3 and 4.

We compare the end-to-end NODE-WSS model to the NODE-EKF approach outlined in Algorithm 2, and DMD-KF method, where a Kalman filter is used instead of an EKF, i.e., the Jacobian in Algorithm 2 is replaced by the diagonal matrix of the DMD eigenvalues. In both filters, the covariance matrices introduced in Sec. IV are set to $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}_d$ and $\mathbf{R} = 0.01\mathbf{I}_{N_s}$ for the modal and the measurement matrices, respectively, where \mathbf{I}_d is the $d \times d$ identity matrix, and \mathbf{I}_{N_s} is the $N_s \times N_s$ identity

FIG. 11: Comparison of the SPOD energy spectra from various ROMs. The lines are obtained by summing the modal energies. The SPOD hyperparameters are: 64 discrete Fourier transform points, 7 temporal blocks with 20 overlapping snapshots, and the Hennig window function.

matrix. Furthermore, we compare the results to an end-to-end LSTM-WSS model, where an LSTM network, with the same number of trainable parameters, replaces the NODE model within the NODE-WSS framework described earlier. Similar to the comparison between the ROMs presented in Fig. 10, we compare in Fig. 13 the temporal average RMSE of the reconstructed flow fields from the various filtering approaches with the best achievable low-rank POD approximation. The results show that end-to-end models are more accurate than the Kalman filtering approaches. We note that tuning the covariance matrices in the (extended) Kalman filter did not further improve the results. Among the models, NODE-WSS is the most accurate model, outperforming LSTM-WSS. Focusing on the best-performing end-to-end models and considering only the last 100 timesteps, NODE-WSS achieved an RMSE of 0.0076 ms^{-1} , which is lower than the 0.0090 ms^{-1} RMSE of LSTM-WSS.

Compared to the predictions of the NODE ROM alone, incorporating all wall shear stress measurements reduced the RMSE by 12.43%. The sensitivity of the predictions to the number of sensors will be examined in the following section. Figure 14 illustrates the radial and axial velocity components predicted with wall shear stress measurements at the same validation timestep shown earlier. The snapshots show very good agreement with the ground truth solution. Particularly, the vortex formation around the stagnation point and the vortex shedding are better approximated near the sensor locations (see Fig. 15 for corresponding sensor locations), with minimal discrepancies farther in the radial direction due to the absence of sensors in this region. Additionally, we note that combining the DMD model with the Kalman filter yields a reliable model that does not progressively damp the predictions, thanks to the update of measurements at each timestep.

C. Sensitivity of predictions to the number of sensors

We evaluate first the sensitivity of the predictions to the number of polarographic sensors using the Kalman filter with the DMD model. We evaluate DMD-KF by progressively adding polarographic sensors from w_1 to w_4 , and computing the rate of improvement in the temporal average RMSE over using only the DMD model is shown in the second column of Tab. II. The results indicate that incorporating more polarographic sensors gradually improves predictions. However, including sensor 4 does not lead to a significant improvement. This is primarily due to the linear measurement model used in the Kalman filter between the temporal coefficient and the wall shear stress signals, which fails to predict w_4 signal outside the fitting zone (see Fig. 5). We expect that using a nonlinear measurement model would enhance its integration into the model. We note that all covariance matrices are set to $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}_r$ and $\mathbf{R} = 0.01\mathbf{I}_{N_s}$, except for the case with 4 sensors, where the last diagonal entry of \mathbf{R} is set to 10 to account for the corresponding low-fidelity measurement. Figure 15 visualizes the relative error between the ground truth and the predictions obtained from DMD and DMD-KF with various number of sensors at timestep 475. It can be clearly seen that incorporating more wall shear stress sensors reduces the prediction error. Specifically, sensors w_1 and w_2 reduce the error in the vortex formation around the stagnation point, with minimal visual differences between the 2 cases for radial and axial velocity components. Including sensor w_3 results in reducing the error in the radial direction for both velocity components, with more accurate approximations on the flow side where the sensors are located. Finally, including sensor w_4 does not bring more improvement due to the low-fidelity measurement model mentioned earlier.

TABLE II: Sensitivity of predictions to the number of sensors. The sensors are added from w_1 to w_4 , where w_1 is located at radius 3.4 mm. The numbers represent the rate of improvement over the corresponding baseline model.

Number of Polaro-graphic sensors	DMD-KF [%]	NODE-WSS [%]
1	7.03	7.99
2	9.23	11.01
3	13.25	11.54
4	13.39	12.43

Similarly, we evaluate the sensitivity of NODE-WSS to the number of sensors and compute the rate of improvement over the NODE model. This analysis is more complex due to the involvement of neural networks with many trainable parameters, unlike the DMD-KF case, which primary requires tuning of the covariance matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} . For consistency, we maintain the same architecture of the end-to-end model with 4 sensors, adjusting only the input layer to match the varying number of sensors in our sensitivity analysis. In each scenario, we train the neural network 100 times with different random initialization of weights and biases, selecting the best-performing model from these trials. This approach helps

FIG. 12: Time series for the temporal coefficients corresponding to the six most dominant energy modes taking into consideration the available wall shear stress measurements. The blue solid line corresponds to the ground truth values, and the orange dashed line shows the NODE-WSS predictions. The initial condition for the NODE-WSS model is the vector of temporal coefficients corresponding to timestep 150.

mitigate the stochastic effects of parameter initialization during training. The rate of improvement over the NODE model without wall shear stress is presented in the third column of Tab. II. As expected, the results show a similar trend to the DMD-KF. Specifically, the addition of the first sensor yields the most significant improvement. A key observed difference is the minimal improvement when increasing from 2 to 3 sensors. It is challenging to distinguish whether this behavior arises from the network structure or from the input information. Nonetheless, adding more sensors gradually improves the performance to achieve 12.43% improvement over the NODE model for the end-to-end model with 4 sensors. This configuration corresponds to the best model in our study with an RMSE of 0.0049 ms^{-1} .

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we explore and demonstrate the capabilities of neural ordinary differential equations (NODEs) for reduced-order modeling in complex flow behavior of impinging jet, comparing it with commonly used methods. Our results reveal that NODE can model the temporal state transition with a slightly higher accuracy than the LSTM architecture. We

note that the primary advantage of NODE lies in its robustness across different initial conditions, requiring only a single initial condition for simulation. In contrast, the LSTM model, despite having a comparable error margin, requires a temporal series of initial conditions. Although it can be argued, that this LSTM limitation can be rectified by using varying lengths of training data batches, it would inevitably lead to longer training time and increased size of training dataset. Additionally, our experiments show that NODE is less likely to overfit during training.

Including the wall shear stress measurements in predictions led to higher accuracy predictions, as evidenced by the simulated results. Our key finding is that the so-called end-to-end filtering outperforms the use of a Kalman filter. The poorer performance of the Kalman filter can be attributed to the introduction of additional errors contained within the linear measurement model. However, end-to-end filtering embeds within its architecture a nonlinear map from the actual wall shear stress measurements to the corresponding states.

In line with this study, we plan to focus on various implicit neural network model architectures, such as continuous-time recurrent neural networks and continuous-time gated recurrent units in modeling flow fields. We also aim to develop model structures with improved capabilities for mod-

FIG. 13: Comparison of the temporal average RMSE for various filtering methods. The presented values are the average of both velocity components. POD truncation yields the best achievable error.

eling stochastic dynamics.

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DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

- ¹P. Bakke, "An experimental investigation of a wall jet," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **2**, 467–472 (1957).
- ²R. A. Bajura and A. A. Szewczyk, "Experimental investigation of a laminar two-dimensional plane wall jet," *The Physics of Fluids* **13**, 1653–1664 (1970).
- ³J. Hall and D. Ewing, "On the dynamics of the large-scale structures in round impinging jets," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **555**, 439–458 (2006).
- ⁴M. D. Deshpande and R. N. Vaishnav, "Submerged laminar jet impingement on a plane," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **114**, 213–236 (1982).
- ⁵J. E. Jaramillo, C.-D. Perez-Segarra, I. Rodriguez, and A. Oliva, "Numerical study of plane and round impinging jets using RANS models," *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals* **54**, 213–237 (2008).

- ⁶M. Bouainouche, N. Bourabaa, and B. Desmet, "Numerical study of the wall shear stress produced by the impingement of a plane turbulent jet on a plate," *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow* **7**, 548–564 (1997).
- ⁷R. D. Plant, J. Friedman, and M. Z. Saghir, "A review of jet impingement cooling," *International Journal of Thermofluids* **17**, 100312 (2023).
- ⁸M. Javidan and A. J. Moghadam, "Experimental investigation on thermal management of a photovoltaic module using water-jet impingement cooling," *Energy Conversion and Management* **228**, 113686 (2021).
- ⁹S. Polat, "Heat and mass transfer in impingement drying," *Drying Technology* **11**, 1147–1176 (1993).
- ¹⁰F. Monnoyer and D. Locheignies, "Heat transfer and flow characteristics of the cooling system of an industrial glass tempering unit," *Applied Thermal Engineering* **28**, 2167–2177 (2008).
- ¹¹N. Wang, A. F. Chen, M. Zhang, and J.-C. Han, "Turbine blade leading edge cooling with one row of normal or tangential impinging jets," *Journal of Heat Transfer* **140**, 062201 (2018).
- ¹²M. Sabato, A. Fregni, E. Stalio, F. Brusiani, M. Tranchero, and T. Baritaud, "Numerical study of submerged impinging jets for power electronics cooling," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* **141**, 707–718 (2019).
- ¹³M. K. Looney and J. J. Walsh, "Mean-flow and turbulent characteristics of free and impinging jet flows," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **147**, 397–429 (1984).
- ¹⁴P. Bradshaw and E. Love, "The normal impingement of a circular air jet over a flat surface," *C. Report and Memo* **3205** (1959).
- ¹⁵A. Rubel, "Computations of jet impingement on a flat surface," *AIAA Journal* **18**, 168–175 (1980).
- ¹⁶J. L. Lumley, "The structure of inhomogeneous turbulence," *Atmospheric Turbulence and Wave Propagation* **21**, 166 – 178 (1967).
- ¹⁷K. Fukami, T. Nakamura, and K. Fukagata, "Convolutional neural network based hierarchical autoencoder for nonlinear mode decomposition of fluid field data," *Physics of Fluids* **32** (2020).
- ¹⁸K. D. Sommer, L. Reineking, Y. P. Ravichandran, R. Skoda, and M. Mönningmann, "Estimating flow fields with reduced order models," *Heliyon* **9**, e20930 (2023).
- ¹⁹P. J. Schmid, "Dynamic mode decomposition of numerical and experimental data," *Journal of fluid mechanics* **656**, 5–28 (2010).
- ²⁰D. Xiao, F. Fang, C. Pain, and G. Hu, "Non-intrusive reduced-order modelling of the Navier–Stokes equations based on RBF interpolation," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids* **79**, 580–595 (2015).
- ²¹S. Pawar, S. M. Rahman, H. Vaddirreddy, O. San, A. Rasheed, and P. Vedula, "A deep learning enabler for nonintrusive reduced order modeling of fluid flows," *Physics of Fluids* **31** (2019).
- ²²P. Wu, J. Sun, X. Chang, W. Zhang, R. Arcucci, Y. Guo, and C. C. Pain, "Data-driven reduced order model with temporal convolutional neural network," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* **360**, 112766 (2020).
- ²³Z. Wang, D. Xiao, F. Fang, R. Govindan, C. C. Pain, and Y. Guo, "Model identification of reduced order fluid dynamics systems using deep learning," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids* **86**, 255–268 (2018).
- ²⁴S. Akbari, S. Pawar, and O. San, "Numerical assessment of a nonintrusive surrogate model based on recurrent neural networks and proper orthogonal decomposition: Rayleigh–Bénard convection," *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics* **36**, 599–617 (2022).
- ²⁵H. Eivazi, H. Veisi, M. H. Naderi, and V. Esfahanian, "Deep neural networks for nonlinear model order reduction of unsteady flows," *Physics of Fluids* **32** (2020).
- ²⁶R. Maulik, B. Lusch, and P. Balaprakash, "Reduced-order modeling of advection-dominated systems with recurrent neural networks and convolutional autoencoders," *Physics of Fluids* **33** (2021).
- ²⁷P. Wu, F. Qiu, W. Feng, F. Fang, and C. Pain, "A non-intrusive reduced order model with transformer neural network and its application," *Physics of Fluids* **34** (2022).
- ²⁸O. San, R. Maulik, and M. Ahmed, "An artificial neural network framework for reduced order modeling of transient flows," *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation* **77**, 271–287 (2019).
- ²⁹Q. Zhuang, J. M. Lorenzi, H.-J. Bungartz, and D. Hartmann, "Model order reduction based on Runge–Kutta neural networks," *Data-Centric Engineering* **2**, e13 (2021).

- ³⁰H. F. Lui and W. R. Wolf, “Construction of reduced-order models for fluid flows using deep feedforward neural networks,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **872**, 963–994 (2019).
- ³¹R. T. Q. Chen, Y. Rubanova, J. Bettencourt, and D. K. Duvenaud, “Neural ordinary differential equations,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vol. 31, edited by S. Bengio, H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, K. Grauman, N. Cesa-Bianchi, and R. Garnett (Curran Associates, Inc., 2018).
- ³²Z. Long, Y. Lu, and B. Dong, “PDE-net 2.0: Learning PDEs from data with a numeric-symbolic hybrid deep network,” *Journal of Computational Physics* **399**, 108925 (2019).
- ³³S. L. Brunton, J. L. Proctor, and J. N. Kutz, “Discovering governing equations from data by sparse identification of nonlinear dynamical systems,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **113**, 3932–3937 (2016).
- ³⁴R. Maulik, A. Mohan, B. Lusch, S. Madireddy, P. Balaprakash, and D. Livescu, “Time-series learning of latent-space dynamics for reduced-order model closure,” *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena* **405**, 132368 (2020).
- ³⁵C. J. Rojas, A. Dengel, and M. D. Ribeiro, “Reduced-order model for fluid flows via neural ordinary differential equations,” arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.02248 (2021).
- ³⁶D. Kanaa, V. Voleti, S. E. Kahou, and C. Pal, “Simple video generation using neural ODEs,” (2021), arXiv:2109.03292.
- ³⁷S. Dutta, P. Rivera-Casillas, and M. W. Farthing, “Neural ordinary differential equations for data-driven reduced order modeling of environmental hydrodynamics,” (2021), arXiv:2104.13962.
- ³⁸M. El Hassan, H. H. Assoum, V. Sobolik, J. Vétel, K. Abed-Meraim, A. Garon, and A. Sakout, “Experimental investigation of the wall shear stress and the vortex dynamics in a circular impinging jet,” *Experiments in Fluids* **52**, 1475–1489 (2012).
- ³⁹M. El Hassan, H. H. Assoum, R. Martinuzzi, V. Sobolik, K. Abed-Meraim, and A. Sakout, “Experimental investigation of the wall shear stress in a circular impinging jet,” *Physics of Fluids* **25**, 077101 (2013).
- ⁴⁰A. Güemes, S. Discetti, and A. Ianiro, “Sensing the turbulent large-scale motions with their wall signature,” *Physics of Fluids* **31** (2019).
- ⁴¹L. Guastoni, A. Güemes, A. Ianiro, S. Discetti, P. Schlatter, H. Azizpour, and R. Vinuesa, “Convolutional-network models to predict wall-bounded turbulence from wall quantities,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **928**, A27 (2021).
- ⁴²J. Boree, “Extended proper orthogonal decomposition: a tool to analyse correlated events in turbulent flows,” *Experiments in fluids* **35**, 188–192 (2003).
- ⁴³Z. Hosseini, R. J. Martinuzzi, and B. R. Noack, “Modal energy flow analysis of a highly modulated wake behind a wall-mounted pyramid,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **798**, 717–750 (2016).
- ⁴⁴R. E. Kalman, “A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems,” *Transactions of the ASME—Journal of Basic Engineering* **82**, 35–45 (1960).
- ⁴⁵N. J. Nair and A. Goza, “Leveraging reduced-order models for state estimation using deep learning,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **897**, R1 (2020).
- ⁴⁶N. B. Erichson, L. Mathelin, Z. Yao, S. L. Brunton, M. W. Mahoney, and J. N. Kutz, “Shallow neural networks for fluid flow reconstruction with limited sensors,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society A* **476**, 20200097 (2020).
- ⁴⁷K. Fukami, R. Maulik, N. Ramachandra, K. Fukagata, and K. Taira, “Global field reconstruction from sparse sensors with Voronoi tessellation-assisted deep learning,” *Nature Machine Intelligence* **3**, 945–951 (2021).
- ⁴⁸J. Wu, D. Xiao, and M. Luo, “Deep-learning assisted reduced order model for high-dimensional flow prediction from sparse data,” *Physics of Fluids* **35** (2023).
- ⁴⁹Z. Li, C. He, and Y. Liu, “Turbulent mean flow prediction in impinging jets using data assimilation methods,” *Physics of Fluids* **36**, 035123 (2024).
- ⁵⁰A. Güemes, S. Discetti, A. Ianiro, B. Sirmacek, H. Azizpour, and R. Vinuesa, “From coarse wall measurements to turbulent velocity fields through deep learning,” *Physics of Fluids* **33** (2021).
- ⁵¹A. Xuan and L. Shen, “Reconstruction of three-dimensional turbulent flow structures using surface measurements for free-surface flows based on a convolutional neural network,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **959**, A34 (2023).
- ⁵²P. J. Schmid, “Dynamic mode decomposition and its variants,” *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics* **54**, 225–254 (2022).
- ⁵³S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, “Long short-term memory,” *Neural Computation* **9**, 1735–1780 (1997).
- ⁵⁴L. Pontryagin, V. Boltyanskii, R. Gamkrelidze, and L. Neustadt, *The Mathematical Theory of Optimal Processes* (Wiley-Interscience, 1962).
- ⁵⁵A. Gholami, K. Keutzer, and G. Biros, “ANODE: Unconditionally accurate memory-efficient gradients for neural ODEs,” (2019), arXiv:1902.10298 [cs.LG].
- ⁵⁶J. Zhuang, N. Dvornek, X. Li, S. Tatikonda, X. Papademetris, and J. Duncan, “Adaptive checkpoint adjoint method for gradient estimation in neural ODE,” in *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning*, Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, Vol. 119, edited by H. D. III and A. Singh (PMLR, 2020) pp. 11639–11649.
- ⁵⁷R. Hasani, M. Lechner, A. Amini, D. Rus, and R. Grosu, “Liquid time-constant networks,” *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* **35**, 7657–7666 (2021).
- ⁵⁸P. Werbos, “Backpropagation through time: what it does and how to do it,” *Proceedings of the IEEE* **78**, 1550–1560 (1990).
- ⁵⁹D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, “Adam: A method for stochastic optimization,” in *Proceedings of the 3rd international conference on learning representations (ICLR)* (arXiv, 2014).
- ⁶⁰O. T. Schmidt and T. Colonius, “Guide to spectral proper orthogonal decomposition,” *AIAA Journal* **58**, 1023–1033 (2020).
- ⁶¹K. Jambunathan, E. Lai, M. Moss, and B. Button, “A review of heat transfer data for single circular jet impingement,” *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow* **13**, 106–115 (1992).

FIG. 14: Comparison of snapshots obtained from various filtering methods incorporating wall shear stress measurements at validation timestep 420.

FIG. 15: Comparison of the relative error between the ground truth snapshot and predictions from DMD and DMD-KF models with varying numbers of sensors at timestep 475. The black squares denote the sensor location.